

Transition Metal Complexes of Heterocyclic Ligand. Part-IV : Studies on Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Pyrrolidonates with Some Heterocyclic Amines and Diamines

(Mrs.) P. R. SHUKLA* and JAYANT BHARGAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226 007

and

GOPAL NARAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Sagar, Sagar-470 003

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THE ligand 2-pyrrolidone possessing two possible sites for coordination (NH and CO groups) has been used as a ligand either as such or as Schiff's bases and also as oxime^{1,2}. The present paper reports the studies on some mixed ligand heterocyclic amine and diamine complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) pyrrolidonates.

Experimental

Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) pyrrolidonates were obtained by treating sodium pyrrolidonate with an aqueous solution of Cu(II), Ni(II) or Co(II) sulphate. On the basis of chemical analyses the compounds

obtained are assigned the formulae $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Synthesis of the complexes :

The complexes are synthesised by taking a suspension of a known amount of metal(II) pyrrolidonate in methanol and adding to it an equimolar amount of the ligand. The reaction mixture is then refluxed for 10 hr. The complexes are crystallised out from the solution by treatment with petroleum spirit.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of elemental analyses and molar conductance studies (Table 1) the following molecular formulae have been assigned to the complexes: $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{am})_2 \text{ or } \text{dam}]$ and $[\text{Ni or Co}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{dam})_2]$. It is evident that the free pyrrolidone has been converted into its uninegative pyrrolidonate ion. This deprotonation is further confirmed by the ir data where the NH stretching frequency of the free ligand at 3310 cm^{-1} is observed to disappear in the complexes. The coordination of pyrrolidonate ion is supported by the distinct lowering of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ from 1700 to $1650 \text{ cm}^{-1,3,4}$. The coordination of different amines is indicated by the shifts in the position of the relevant infrared bands⁵⁻¹¹. The presence of lattice water in almost all the complexes is shown by the presence of a band at 3515 cm^{-1} .

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA

Complex	Colour	Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)				Δ_M $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	C	H	N		
1. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{py})_2]$	Olive green	16.24 (16.54)	55.10 (55.46)	5.90 (5.65)	15.25 (15.75)	0.90	1.90
2. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{4-pic})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	12.01 (12.99)	51.00 (50.23)	6.42 (6.95)	11.65 (11.84)	0.69	2.16
3. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{8-pio})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Olive green	20.41 (12.99)	50.54 (50.23)	7.51 (6.95)	11.82 (11.44)	0.75	2.07
4. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{7-pio})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Olive green	12.08 (12.99)	49.92 (50.23)	6.62 (6.95)	11.08 (11.44)	0.95	2.04
5. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{en})] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Olive green	15.42 (16.28)	33.53 (33.03)	9.52 (9.70)	15.65 (15.41)	1.05	1.83
6. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{pn})] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Ink blue	17.06 (16.84)	34.15 (34.94)	7.54 (7.95)	14.85 (14.33)	8.58	1.99
7. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{dipy})] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Bottle green	12.38 (12.90)	43.28 (43.81)	6.95 (6.50)	11.28 (10.96)	1.00	2.02
8. $[\text{Cu}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{phen})] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Ink blue	11.24 (11.83)	44.28 (44.81)	6.81 (6.35)	10.34 (10.09)	0.56	2.15
9. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{en})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Pink	13.02 (13.95)	34.52 (34.34)	8.92 (8.58)	20.63 (20.04)	0.61	3.00
10. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{pn})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Pink	13.54 (13.12)	37.18 (37.61)	8.72 (8.96)	18.65 (18.80)	0.78	3.39
11. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{dipy})_2] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Bright pink	9.86 (9.65)	55.42 (55.01)	5.28 (5.89)	13.15 (13.76)	0.72	3.65
12. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{phen})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dirty pink	8.56 (8.49)	55.92 (55.27)	6.05 (5.76)	12.51 (12.09)	1.01	3.48
13. $[\text{Co}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{en})_2] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brown	12.60 (12.95)	31.92 (31.65)	8.90 (8.79)	18.18 (18.47)	0.46	4.66
14. $[\text{Co}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{pn})_2] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brown	10.92 (11.19)	35.08 (34.75)	9.48 (9.13)	17.62 (17.38)	1.02	4.69
15. $[\text{Co}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{dipy})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orangish brown	9.02 (9.64)	54.62 (54.99)	5.08 (5.65)	13.68 (13.75)	0.48	4.70
16. $[\text{Co}(\text{pyrr})_2(\text{phen})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orangish brown	8.02 (8.48)	54.95 (55.25)	5.40 (5.75)	12.50 (12.09)	0.76	4.65

* Author for correspondence.

Thus it appears that the copper(II) complexes are four coordinate while the nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes are six coordinate, and in all of them the pyrrolidone ion is monodentate, coordinating through >CO group alone and its negative nitrogen simply neutralises the charge of the metal(II) ion.

The copper(II) complexes are paramagnetic with their μ_{eff} values lying in the range of 1.83-2.16 B.M. The appearance of a band between 14.00-18.00 kK with two shoulders at ~ 12.50 and 10.50 kK is indicative of the planar stereochemistry of the complexes. The assignments of the band may be ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ (14.00-18.00 kK), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ (12.50 kK) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ (10.50 kK), respectively. The position of the main band, directly equal to Dq, occurs at ~ 1400 cm^{-1} in the pyridine and picoline complexes and at ~ 1800 cm^{-1} in diamine complexes and correlates well with the position of these ligands in spectrochemical series.

The μ_{eff} values of nickel(II) complexes lie in the range of 3.00-3.65 B.M. indicating high spin octahedral structures. The three bands in the electronic spectra at 25.50, 18.00 and 11.50 kK due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) transitions, respectively and the Dq values of 1150 cm^{-1} are also characteristic of an octahedral structure^{1,2-15}. The ν_3 and ν_2 bands are both split into two components due to the lowering of symmetry on account of the presence of different ligands around the metal.

The cobalt(II) complexes also possess high spin octahedral structures as the μ_{eff} values lie around 4.70 B.M. In the diffuse reflectance spectra, two sharp bands due to ν_3 and ν_1 transitions are observed at 20.00 and 8.00 kK. The shoulder at 15.50 kK is the ν_2 transition as expected. The splitting of the ν_3 transition into two components, one at 20.50 kK and the other at 18.50 kK has been attributed to the lowering of the symmetry of the complexes owing to the coordination of different ligands to cobalt(II). The Dq and B values are around 900 and 1010 cm^{-1} supporting the pseudo-octahedral structures for the complexes¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

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Synthesis and Structural Studies of Some First Row Transition Metal Complexes of Salicylidene Ethyl Carbazate

R. C. AGGARWAL*, N. K. SINGH and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

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ALTHOUGH a number of papers are available on the transition metal complexes of salicylidene alkyl dithiocarbazate and its N- or S-alkyl substituted derivatives^{1,2}, there is no previous report on transition metal complexes of salicylidene derivatives of alkyl carbazates. In view of our earlier work on transition metal complexes of salicylidene derivatives of hydrazine and picolinoyl hydrazine^{3,4}, it was of interest to undertake preparative and structural studies of the salicylidene ethyl carbazate (SEC) complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II). The results of these studies are presented here.

Experimental

Preparation of salicylidene ethyl carbazate (SEC): Salicylidene ethyl carbazate, *o*-OHC₆H₄CH=N-NH-COOC₂H₅, was prepared by reacting salicylaldehyde with ethanolic solution of ethyl carbazate in $\sim 1:1$ molar ratio. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallized from CHCl₃, m.p. 133°. (Found: C, 57.24; H, 5.48; N, 13.15; N₂H₄, 15.24. C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₃ requires C, 57.69; H, 5.76; N, 13.48; N₂H₄, 15.38%). Ethyl carbazate required for the above preparation was obtained by the reaction of diethyl carbonate and hydrazine hydrate following the literature procedure⁵.

Preparation of the complexes: The complexes Cu(SEC-2H)₂.H₂O and M(SEC-H)₂ [M=Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) or Zn(II)] were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of SEC and aqueous solutions of the appropriate metal chloride in 1:1 and 2:1 molar ratio, respectively and raising the pH of the reaction mixture to about 6-7 with dil. NH₄OH solution. The complexes thus precipitated were filtered, washed with CHCl₃ and dried *in vacuo*.